

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SMOC1

(SPARC related modular calcium binding 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	64093 / Q9H4F8
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including MDK and SFRP1 (1,2).

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.14 (rank #179, 99.3th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.14 out of 5 (rank #179, 99.3th percentile). The individual score components include 2.16 of 3 for genetics, and 1.98 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SMOC1, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. The biological domain characterization of the source module (Module 42) indicates that the proteins in this module are enriched for terms annotated to the Structural Stabilization, Synapse, Lipid Metabolism, and APP Metabolism domains. The most significantly enriched terms from this module are “collagen-containing extracellular matrix”, “basement membrane”, and “endoplasmic reticulum lumen”. SMOC1 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization biological domain.

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Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia

patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of SMOC1 is confidently detected in oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC) as well as inhibitory neuron subtypes within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

SMOC1 (SPARC related modular calcium binding 1) is an amyloid plaque associated protein that is implicated in AD pathogenesis and may function as a viable biomarker of disease progression (3–6). However, little is known about the biological role of SMOC1 in the central nervous system, nor what role it may play in AD pathogenesis. Consequently, this project aims to develop resources that will help the scientific community explore the role of SMOC1 in brain and disease. **The aim of this project is to produce TEP reagents to help further understand the biology of SMOC1 in Alzheimer's disease.**

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SMOC1 is a 434 amino acid calcium binding glycoprotein that localizes to the basement membrane, or the extracellular matrix, when secreted (7). In addition to binding calcium, SMOC1 also binds to heparin, potentially modifying the interactions within the extracellular glycoalyx (8). In addition to binding calcium, SMOC1 appears to play a role in the mobilization of intracellular calcium (9) and is involved in the development of bone formation (10–13). Disruption of SMOC1 mediated antagonism of bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) signaling is associated with Waardenburg Anophthalmia, a disorder of the eye and limb development in which altered bone formation drives synostosis, syndactyly, oligodactyly, polydactyly and long bone hypoplasia (14). SMOC1 mediated regulation of BMP signalling is also implicated in aortic valve calcification (15), potentially suggesting broad biological involvement of SMOC1 in calcium-linked developmental and disease related events. Elevated levels of SMOC1 are associated with Low-Grade Glioma (LGG) tumours, and positively correlates with survival likelihood (16–18), suggesting SMOC1 could be a viable biomarker for LGG. In contrast, SMOC1 may be epigenetically silenced within other cancer subtypes (19), suggesting a potential heterogenous role in the regulation of cellular propagation. In brain, SMOC1 is expressed in numerous cell-types, as highlighted in the bioinformatics section above.

The role of SMOC1 in the nervous system is not well understood, but numerous studies of linked altered expression of SMOC1 with Alzheimer's disease (AD) (3–6). One study identified SMOC1 increasing with AD pathology levels in both human and mouse brains, as well as human CSF, suggesting a plausible role as a biomarker for AD pathological progression (6). A second study investigating brain derived CSF protein as biomarkers for AD also found SMOC1 as one of the most plausible discriminators between AD cases and controls (5). Similarly, a third study using a varied mass spectrometry protocol also identified SMOC1 as significantly upregulated in Alzheimer's patients (4). Concordantly, a recent study investigating the amyloid plaque associated proteome in early onset AD, Down Syndrome (DS), and late onset AD by laser capture plaque purification from the hippocampus followed by mass spectrometry characterization of the proteome identified SMOC1 as one of the top 10 plaque associated proteins across disease states (3). Further suggesting that SMOC1 may be linked with clinical disease progression, SMOC1 was identified to a module (Module 42) that is highly correlated with cognitive decline in brain proteomic studies (1,2). All of

this suggests that SMOC1 may play a role in AD pathogenesis, and may play an informative role as a biomarker of disease progression.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for SMOC1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for SMOC1 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

Complete report: [YCharOS SMOC1 Antibody Characterization Report](#)

Proteins Purified

1. SMOC1_35-434_HisN_A: Human SMOC1, a.a.35-434. Protein produced in SF9 cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Cell type specific expression: Using anti-human SMOC1 antibody ab313569 as appears in the [YCharOS SMOC1 Antibody Characterization Report](#), SMOC1 expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived neurons and astrocytes but minimally detected in human iPSC-derived microglia (Fig. 1). See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 1. Expression of SMOC1 in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples (n=2) were run in adjacent lanes.

Protein localization in AD and control brain: protein localization by immunohistochemistry

Biological probe discovery:

1) Cell-based assays following treatment with recombinant protein

To understand the impact of modulating SMOC1 on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with recombinant SMOC1. WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with recombinant SMOC1 before measuring cell viability (Fig. 2A), cytotoxicity (Fig. 2B), and mitochondrial function (Fig. 2C). Treatment with recombinant SMOC1 protein did not have any toxic effects on the astrocytes as indicated by the AlamarBlue and LDH experiments. Recombinant SMOC1 protein treatment did not have any significant effect on mitochondrial function. See **Additional Information** for experimental details.

Figure 2. Activity of WTC11 iPSC-derived astrocytes following SMOC1 protein treatment. A) AlamarBlue viability assay B) LDH cytotoxicity assay C) Mitotracker assay, $n=3$ independent experiments, $*p<0.05$. BSA serves as control.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of SMOC1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

1. SMOC1_35-434_HisN_AviC PBC040C11

Gene name	SMOC1
Uniprot ID	Q9H4F8
Region	35-434

Description	Plays essential roles in both eye and limb development. Probable regulator of osteoblast differentiation
Synonyms	SPARC-related modular calcium-binding protein 1
Construct ID	SMOC1_35-434_HisN_AviC PBC040C11
Parental Vector	pFHMSp-AviN-LIC-C
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMD
Tag (C-terminal)	SSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE
Protein mass (with tag)	52324.06Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	54205
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMD LISDRDPQCNLH CSRTQPKPICASDGRSYESMCEYQRAKCRDPTLGVVHRGRCKDAGQSKCRLERAQALEQ AKKPQEAVFVPEGGEDGSFTQVQCHTYTGYCWCVTPDGKPISSVQNKTPVCSGSVTD KPLSQGNSGRKDDGSKPTPTMETQPVFDGDEITAPTLWIKHLVIKDSKLNNTNIRNSEKVV SCDQERQSALEEAQQNPREGIVIECAPGGLYKPVQCHQSTGYCWCVLVDTGRPLPGTST RYVMPSCESDARAKTTEADDPFKDRELPGCPEGKKMEFITSLLDALTTDMVQAINSAAPT GGGRFSEPDPSHTLEERVVHWYFSQLDSNSSNDINKREM KPFKRYVKKKAKPKKARRFT DYCDLNKDKVISLPELKGCLGVSKEGRLVSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
IMAC, Ni (step 1): SMOC1_35-434_HisN_Avi C PBC040C11	

<p>SEC (step 2): SMOC1_35-434_HisN_Avi C PBC040C11</p>	
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>0.25 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p>Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)</p>
<p>Expression Medium</p>	<p>I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre</p>
<p>Transformation and storage</p>	<p>The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.</p>
<p>Expression</p>	<p>For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes are monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.</p>
<p>Purification buffers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. IEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 260 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 6. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
<p>Purification step 1: IMAC</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 1CV of wash buffer. 7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 8. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.

Cell line information

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation (20). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line (21) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described (22). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 µg/mL puromycin, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 µg/µL NAC, 10 µg/µL hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 µg/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described (23). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 µg/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1 µg/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1µg/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates were separated on 10% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with SMOC1 antibody (Abcam, ab313569) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000 at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Protein treatment of cells

iPSc-derived astrocytes were cultured on 96-well plates. Cells were treated with SMOC1 protein (purified in house, see methods above) in 100 µl media on day 14 for 24 hours.

AlamarBlue viability assay

20 µl CellTiter-Blue reagent (Promega, #G8088) was added to each well of a 96-well plate. After incubating for 4 hours at 37°C, Fluorescence Intensity (FI), which corresponds to the number of living cells, was measured with PHERAstar FSX (BMG Labtech) plate reader (Ex. 560nm and Em. 590nm). Wells containing medium only were used to determine background signal.

LDH cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay was performed using kit (Promega, J2380). Cell culture medium was diluted 20 fold with LDH storage buffer (200mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.3), 10% Glycerol, 1% BSA). 50 µl diluted culture medium was mixed with 50 µl LDH detection reagent in a 96-well opaque-walled, non-transparent assay plate with opaque bottom. After 60 minutes incubation at room temperature, luminescence signal was measured with EnVision 2103 Multilabel plate Reader (PerkinElmer).

Mitotracker assay

To stain mitochondria, mitochondrial membrane potential indicator, TMRM (ThermoFisher, #134361), was diluted in culture medium containing the nuclear indicator Hoechst 33342. 5 µl staining solution was added to each well to final concentration of 100 nM TMRM and 10 µg/ml Hoechst 33342. After 30 minutes incubation at 37°C, cells were imaged with ImageXpress® Micro (Molecular Devices), and the fluorescence intensity of the cells was quantified with MetaXpress 6. Carbonyl cyanide-p-trifluoromethoxyphenylhydrazone (FCCP) was used as positive control at 100 µM. 30 minutes before adding staining solution, FCCP was added to cells at final concentration of 100 µM.

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